

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS

Matchanova Nazokat

Urganch State University

2nd year master's student in preschool education

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of interactive pedagogical technologies and methods in improving the professional competence of educators.

Key words: Educational system, educator pedagogue, competence, methodology.

As our time is rapidly developing, a number of changes and reforms are being carried out in the field of education. At the current stage of our society, the problem of raising the young generation to be socially active and creating the necessary conditions for becoming a perfect person is attracting the attention of scientists and specialists. The issue of bringing up the young generation, which is being formed as the creator of the fundamental reforms being implemented in our republic, their education at the level of the requirements of the time, their maturity as a person, the preparation for learning the secrets of the profession and solving everyday tasks, is the main problem of the educational process. is on the agenda. Necessary knowledge and skills are provided for the development of high-quality, perfect personnel, which is the demand of the new era. Also, nowadays, attempts to increase the effectiveness of education using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process, interesting and meaningful training, technological methods for concentration of attention and attention, attention to the use of methods is increasing day by day.

A teacher-pedagogue, like any specialist, has a personal-practical character, appearance and style. Also, he should be able to absorb the concept of competence and be able to use his abilities in any situation, be able to use his knowledge, skills and qualifications, and start pedagogical activities based on it. Trainings conducted on the basis of pedagogical technology-methods satisfy the desire of young people to express their attitudes towards important life achievements and problems, and create an opportunity for them to think and justify their points of view.

In order to solve the problems faced by the educational system in the innovative processes taking place at the present time, we need people who are able to assimilate new information and evaluate their acquired knowledge, who make the necessary decisions, who think independently and freely. Therefore, the role and importance of modern teaching methods, interactive methods, ICT, training, and innovative technologies in the educational process of educational institutions is incomparable. Interactive methods and didactic games provide knowledge, experience, and practical skills related to their use in education, to provide students with knowledge and advanced skills.

If we define the interactive methods in another way, the interactive method is implemented on the basis of the interaction of the students during the educational process. serves to improve knowledge acquisition and develop personal qualities. Using these methods will help

to increase the quality and efficiency of training. The exercises used in modern interactive methods are aimed at helping students to find the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze it independently, and to draw erroneous conclusions by themselves. In this process, the pedagogue creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and education of the team, and at the same time, he performs the functions of management and guidance. First of all, a pedagogue should be a master of his profession, possess skills, and know his professional qualities.

The qualities of professional competence are as follows:

1. Social competence.

- 1) possession of skills and qualifications to interact with social organizations and subjects;
- 2) ability to master professional communication and behavior styles;

2. Personal competence.

- 1) to constantly achieve professional growth and improve professional qualifications;
- 2) being able to realize one's own potential in professional activity;

3. Special competence.

- 1) preparing to organize professional-pedagogical activities independently;
- 2) having the ability to correctly solve the usual professional and pedagogical tasks and realistically evaluate the results of one's work;
- 3) having the ability to independently and consistently acquire new knowledge and skills in the specialty;

4. Technological competence.

- 1) ability to master advanced technologies that enrich professional-pedagogical knowledge, skills and qualifications;
- 2) the ability to use modern didactic tools (technical tools, educational tools);

5. Extreme competence.

- 1) in emergency situations (in case of natural disasters, technological process failure), ability to make rational decisions and act correctly;
- 2) in problematic situations (when pedagogical conflicts arise), it is to have the skills to make a rational decision, to act correctly.

To analyze the essence of the concept of "professional competence", to present it as an integration of knowledge, skills, competences and professionally important personal qualities that reflect the pedagogue's ability to effectively implement professional activities and achieve goals related to personality development in the preschool education system allows. As a result of the analysis of pedagogical experience and scientific research on a global scale, it has been proven that 70% of all the knowledge that a person acquires during his life is acquired by the age of five. That is why in the preschool period, the child and the teacher work together. they go, that is, they act as leaders. It is useful and necessary to improve the methodology of developing creative competence of future experts working in preschool educational organizations based on an integrative approach, and further improve it by fully completing the training activities. shows aspects. A pedagogue working in pre-school educational organizations to develop the creative abilities of the growing young generation to fully respond to the demands of the new age, to creatively approach any situation, to understand the world with new views, to form creative thinking and thinking in them, demands creative competence from specialists in their professional activities.

A preschool teacher should have the following social and professional competencies that allow children to develop cognitively:

1. Social competencies include the exchange of information between individuals, the expression of their interests and needs, the manifestation of tolerance towards other people and their opinions, the ability to work in a team and various support for other people with emotional stability includes the ability to give;
2. Cognitive competences are manifested in independent processing and structure of information, searching for new sources of information, concentrating on studying or working, ability to use acquired knowledge and skills.
3. Operational competences - setting goals and work order, the ability to resist ambiguity and uncertainty, the ability to make and implement decisions, summarize work results, determine the work schedule;
4. Specific competencies include problem solving, self-management, being active in professional activities, adapting to new situations, evaluating and correcting plans, identifying errors and planning adequate ways to eliminate them.

Therefore, professional competences are the basis for introducing a competence approach to the pedagogical process and help the preschool educator to implement knowledge, skills and abilities in the implementation of innovative activities and the practical use of modern educational technologies. must have: understanding, benevolent, sincere, friendly, polite, sense of humor, patient, establish relationships with children, prevent and resolve conflicts, o He should supplement his knowledge through self-education, know the method of preschool education and education.

Also, the educator must have the characteristics of mental activity: verbal-logical memory, the characteristics of activity goals: involuntary memory, short-term memory according to the retention period of the material. the ability to control them, a strong nervous system is necessary: the educator's work continues in conditions of constant psycho-emotional stress, even if it does not increase with physical strength.

In conclusion, the future pedagogue should have deep knowledge and the ability to work effectively, he should have sufficient theoretical and practical knowledge and skills in the fundamentals of science, effective use of new pedagogical and information technologies and methods in the educational process. it depends on how well the qualification is formed. Being able to understand the concept of competence, be able to use them, make the training interesting and effective in an interactive way will further improve their thinking and the scope of knowledge. Currently, the development and wide application of information and communication technologies is a global direction of world development. In today's rapidly growing period of information technology education, it will be possible to achieve the effectiveness of education and education even if such practical work of creating electronic education resources is carried out.

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